

Development of the Renewable Energy-Based Distributed Generation Electricity System at Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe

Rusli¹, Jufriadi², Teuku Hasannuddin³, Anita Fauziah⁴, Muhammad Syahroni⁵,
Zulfikar⁶, Akhyar⁷

^{1,3,4,5,6,7}Electrical Engineering Department, Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe, Indonesia;

²Mechanical Engineering Department, Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe, Indonesia;

*Corresponding author: jufriadi@pnl.ac.id

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8004956

Received : March, 15, 2023

Accepted : April 15, 2023

Online : April 30, 2023

Abstract – Solar power plants (PLTS) are a type of renewable energy-based distributed generation electricity system. A distributed generation-based electricity system is a decentralized electricity system that places power plants in each city or in areas with power shortages, as well as possibly in load centers. The generator can be used as an energy supplier during normal loads, peak loads, or as backup power in the event of a disturbance to ensure system reliability. The goal of this research is to convert solar energy into electrical energy in order to meet the electrical energy needs of the Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe environment and to demonstrate the existence of energy efficiency in the 20 kV electrical system. The design of a 1 MW solar power plant begins with selecting a building with a wide and high roof so that sunlight is not obstructed, the angle of inclination for the placement of solar panels following the slope of the building's roof, a circuit system between solar panels and batteries, the number of solar panels and batteries required, inverter power capacity, battery control system, and the transformer capacity to be used. The design results for the capacity for generating electrical energy are incorporated into the 20 kV Aceh distribution network, transforming it into an interconnection system based on distributed generation. The power flow of a distributed generation electric power system is analyzed using the Newton-Raphson method to determine power losses and voltage drop. According to the study's findings, the design of a solar power plant in the Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe Area produced an effective power of 1.3 MW with electrical energy during the planned operating hours of 24 hours to serve the load continuously without disconnection. According to the findings of this study, the components required to generate 1 MW of power are 64132 60 WP solar panels with a land area of 25655 m², 12800 200Ah batteries, 75 5 kVA inverters, and 51 transformers 20 kV 25 kVA. Power losses at the Bayu Substation - PNL Genset House were reduced by 0.605 kVA or 72% after optimization with the addition of a 20 kV distributed generation electrical system in the Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic environment at 80% penetration. At 80% penetration, the smallest voltage drop on the Bayu Substation - PNL Genset House is 0.078% or 0.02 kV. This indicates that the voltage drop at the Bayu Substation - PNL Genset House has been reduced by 0.135%.

Keywords: Solar Power Plant, Renewable Energy, Distributed Generation Electricity System.

Introduction

Solar power plants, also known as PLTS, are essentially electricity sources that can generate varying amounts of power, either independently or in conjunction with other energy sources. These plants utilize both decentralized and centralized methods to generate electricity. The key feature of PLTS is its reliance on solar energy, which is an abundant and renewable resource. Additionally, PLTS is an environmentally friendly option as it lacks rotating components, produces no noise, and does not emit exhaust gases or waste [1].

Indonesia, with its tropical climate, has a significant potential for solar energy, estimated at 4.8 kWh/m²/day. Lhokseumawe City, specifically the Gampoeng Jeulikat Muara Dua Subdistrict situated on a plateau at an elevation of 21 m (coordinates 5.13512, 97.10838), possesses favorable conditions for the installation of solar panels with a capacity of 10 MW. Previous studies conducted by the P2M unit of Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe focused on PLTD plant types within the 150 kV Aceh interconnection system. Optimum

energy efficiency is achieved at a 90% penetration level, with a substantial amount of wasted energy amounting to 0.309 MW prior to distributed generation reaching 27.248 MW [2].

Aligned with the research strategic plan of Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe, which prioritizes electrical energy conversion, the objective of this research is to develop new and renewable energy technologies by harnessing the local resource potential. The design of solar power plants is aimed at achieving optimal energy production. Key components of these plants, including solar panels, batteries, inverters, and charge controllers, are employed to ensure efficiency. To enhance reliability, the generated energy will be distributed through a medium voltage network operating at 20 kV.

Materials and Methods

a. Research Location

The main focus of this study will take place at Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe (PNL), which is situated in Blang Mangat District, Lhokseumawe City, Aceh. The roofs of various structures within the PNL campus, including the Main Building, Electrical Engineering Building, Chemical Engineering Building, Civil Engineering Building, Mechanical Engineering Building, KPA Building, Equipment Building, Dormitory Building, Auditorium Building, Commerce Building, and Mosque, will be utilized as sites for the installation of solar panels.

b. Research Stage

The following are the research stages completed by the research to design solar power plants as distributed generation in the 20 kV interconnection system:

1. Solar Power Plant Design Model
2. The 1 MW solar power plant design is made up of 60 watt 18.2 Volt solar panels and is connected to a 20 kV distribution network system. A series of solar panels connected in parallel generates a voltage of 12-18 volts DC, which is then converted into a 220 volt AC voltage by an inverter.
3. Solar Panel Specifications and Number. There are several types of solar panels, including Morpheus and Compound panels. The most common of these two types are below: Polycrystal, also known as polycrystalline, is a type of solar panel or solar cell with a random arrangement of crystals. Polycrystalline types require a larger surface area to produce the same electrical power as monocrystalline types, but can produce electricity on cloudy days. The most efficient panel, producing the most power per unit area, is monocrystal. It has a 15% efficiency rating. The disadvantage of this type of panel is that it will not work well in areas with little sunlight (shade), and its efficiency will plummet in cloudy weather.
4. Angle of Solar Panel Laying. The angle of the planned solar panels at Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe is leveled by following the slope of the building's roof.
5. Solar Panel Evaluation. In the Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe area, solar panel testing is done using open circuits to obtain voltage values and closed circuits to obtain current values.
6. Using the Measure Map application, calculate the roof area of the building. Solar panels will be installed on the roof of the building at Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe to create a Rooftop PLTS that will serve the electrical load in every PNL study room and laboratory. The roof area of each building in the PNL environment must be measured to obtain electrical power and the number of solar panels. Measurements are taken with the Measure Map application to determine the flat area of each building's roof. Figure 1 shows an example of measurement using Measure Map.

Figure 1. Measuring the roof of the building using Measure Map

7. Determining the number of solar panels

The solar panels are arranged in parallel to obtain power based on the roof area of the building available at PNL. The following formula can be used to calculate the number of solar panels required:

$$NPS = LAG / LPS \tag{1}$$

Description:

LPS = Area of Solar Panels

LAG = Building Roof Area

NPS = Number of Solar Panels.

The number of MS60M-36 Model solar panels for each building in the PNL environment can be calculated using the equation above.

8. Electricity Calculation

The operating time is equal to the illumination time.

The solar panel arrays are arranged in parallel to obtain power based on the available building roof area at PNL. The following formula can be used to calculate the total electrical power generated:

$$PPLTS = PPS \times NPS \tag{2}$$

Description:

PPS = power generated by solar panels

NPS stands for the number of Solar Panels.

PPLTS = Power of PLTS

Irradiation time is not the same as operating time.

The solar panels are arranged in parallel to obtain power based on the roof area of the building available at PNL. The following formula can be used to calculate the total electrical power generated while accounting for PLTS operating hours and solar panel irradiation:

$$NPS \times PPS \times T2 / T1 = PPLTS \tag{3}$$

Description:

PPLTS = Power of PLTS

PPS = power from solar panels

T1 = Time of PLTS operation

T2 = Time spent irradiating solar panels

9. Determining the Number of Batteries

The battery arrangement is built in parallel to generate PLTS power based on the number of solar panels installed in each building in the PNL environment. The number of batteries required can be calculated using the following formula:

$$NB = PPLTS \times T1 \times H0 / VB \times AhB \times B \tag{4}$$

Description:

NB = the number of batteries.

PPLTS = Power of PLTS

- AhB = Ampere Hour Battery
- VB = Battery Voltage
- B = Battery Efficiency
- H0 =denotes the number of days without irradiation.
- T1 = Time of PLTS operation

10. Calculating the number of Inverters

The number of inverters required can be calculated using the following formula:

$$NI = PPLTS / PI \quad (5)$$

Description:

- Ni = number of inverters
- PPLTS = solar panel power
- PI = Inverter Power

11. Calculating the number of transformers

The arrangement is built in parallel to provide power to each building in the PNL environment. The number of 20 kV distribution transformers required can be calculated using the following formula:

$$NTD = PPLTS / PTD \quad (6)$$

Description:

- NTD = number of distribution transformers
- PTD = transformer power.
- PPLTS = PLTS power

12. Data collection for the 20 kV Lhokseumawe distribution system.

13. Collecting 20 kV distribution system data regarding network parameters, peak power demand of Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic. An analysis was performed on the data obtained, and it was organized systematically to be inputted into a simulation program with a penetration rate using the Valerij's Knazkins equation.[12]

14. Power flow simulation of 20 kV distribution system with Newton Raphson method without distributed generation to determine voltage, loss and power factor. Simulation is also carried out for the power flow of 20 kV distribution system with Newton Raphson method based on distributed generation to determine the voltage, loss, and power factor.

The flow chart of this study can be observed in Figure 2 displayed underneath:

Figure 2. Flowchart of Solar Power Plant Design as Distributed Generation

Data collection

Model of a Solar Power Plant

The solar power plant, with a capacity of 1 MW, utilizes solar panels rated at 60 watts and 18.2 volts. These panels are connected to form a series, generating a direct current (DC) voltage ranging from 12 to 18 volts. To convert this DC voltage into alternating current (AC) with a voltage of 220 volts, an inverter is employed. Furthermore, a step-up transformer is used to elevate the AC voltage to 20 kV, which is then connected to the 20 kV interconnection system. The overall configuration of this 1 MW solar power plant, including its interconnections, can be seen in Figure 3 as a single line diagram.

Figure 3. A single-line diagram of the design of a 1 MW 20kV solar power plant

Model MS60M-36 Solar Panel Testing

Figure 4 demonstrates the acquisition of data on current and voltage from the testing of the GL 136-M85 Model Solar Panel at 30-minute intervals.

Figure 4. Charging Current

Figure 4 depicts the highest charging current at 12.00 WIB with a current of 3.562 A. The lowest charging current is 0.373 A and occurs at 08.00 WIB.

Results

The calculation results for the quantity of components needed for the 1 MW PLTS, considering operating hour limitations for each building in the Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic environment, are depicted in Figure 5. This figure illustrates the highest number of solar panels, which amounts to 4310 pieces, with a combined power output of 86 kW, specifically allocated for the civil engineering building.

Figure 5. PLTS Component Recapitulation

Power Flow Simulation of a 20 kV System with a 20 kV Network Configuration Model.

This simulation's network configuration model is based on a network configuration that has been simplified into three zones, namely:

1. The Bayu Substation's Zone 1 grid.
2. Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic Generator House in Zone 2.

3. Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic's Zone 3 PLTS Building.

Figure 6 below illustrates the arrangement of the three zones mentioned earlier in order to design a 20 kV network configuration.

Figure 6. Simulation Model of PNL 20 kV Network configuration

Load and Line Impedance.

The calculation of channel impedance involves multiplying the conductor type, conductor size, and the distance between substations. In the case of the 20 kV Meuredu Pidie Jaya system, the channel impedance is determined by inputting the impedance simulation data from the 70 mm A3CS cable, which has a value of $0.4202 + j 0.3572$ ohm/km, into the equation provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Line impedance

Substation	Cable size(240)		Cable length (KM)	R (OHM)	X (OHM)	Impedance (OHM)
	R (OHM/ KM)	X (OHM/ KM)				
Substation Bayu - Power House PNL	0,4202	0,3572	3	1,2606	1,0716	1,2606 + j1,0716
Power House PNL - Gedung PNL	0,4202	0,3572	0,3	0,1261	0,1071	0,1261 + j0,1071

Power flow simulation before and after DG installation.

Table 2 below presents the outcomes of the power flow simulation for the 20 kV PNL distribution system, both prior to and after the incorporation of distributed generation.

Table 2. Power Flow Results

No	Penetration DG	Power Penetration on DG	Power (kVA)		Voltage Drop n (%)		Power Factor	
			Without DG	DG	Without DG	DG	Without DG	DG
1	20	1000	0,835	0,58	0,213	0,179	0,85	0,85
2	40	2000	0,835	0,40	0,213	0,145	0,85	0,85
3	60	3000	0,835	0,28	0,213	0,111	0,85	0,85
4	80	4000	0,835	0,23	0,213	0,078	0,85	0,85

Table 2 displays the power loss (P) observed on the line with the highest power loss before optimization, without the inclusion of distributed generation, on the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House line. The power loss is measured at 0.835 kW. On the other hand, after incorporating distributed generation with an 80% penetration level, the smallest power loss on the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House line is recorded at 0.23 kW. This indicates a significant 72% reduction in power loss at the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House.

The table also presents the voltage drop on the line where the largest voltage drop occurs prior to optimization, specifically the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House line. The voltage drop is measured at 0.213% or 0.04 kV. However, after the addition of distributed generation with an 80% penetration level, the smallest voltage drop on the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House line is 0.078% or 0.02 kV. This demonstrates a reduction of 0.135% in voltage drop at the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House.

Figures 7 and 8 depict the impact of the penetration percentage of distributed generation on DG power.

Figure 7. Power Loss

Figure 8. Voltage Drops

Conclusion

Research conducted on Development of the renewable energy-based distributed generation electricity system at Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe of a solar power plant, when implemented as a distributed generation in the 20 kV Lhokseumawe distribution system, yields several significant findings:

Firstly, to generate a power output of 1.28 MW continuously for 24 hours, the following components are required: 64132 solar panels with a capacity of 60WP, covering an area of 25655 m²; 12800 batteries with a capacity of 200Ah; 75 inverters with a rating of 5 kVA, and 51 transformers with a rating of 20 kV and 25 kVA.

Furthermore, by optimizing the system with the addition of distributed generation at an 80% penetration rate, the power losses occurring at the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House are reduced significantly. Specifically, the power loss is diminished by 0.605 kVA, amounting to a 72% reduction.

In addition, at this 80% penetration rate, the voltage drops experienced along the Bayu Substation line to the PNL Generator House are minimized. The smallest voltage drop observed is 0.078% or 0.02 kV, showcasing a reduction of 0.135% in voltage drop at the Bayu Substation - PNL Generator House.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe, Indonesia for providing research grant under DIPA PNL 2022.

References

- [1] Pradityo, J., Winardi, B. dan Nugroho, A., 2015, Evaluasi dan Optimalisasi system Off Grid PLTH Bayu Baru, Bantul D.I. Yogyakarta”, Transient Vol 4, No 3.
- [2] Hasanuddin, 2017, “Efisiensi Penggunaan Energi Listrik Pada Sistem Interkoneksi 150kV Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam Menggunakan Distributed Generation”, Jurnal Listrik Telekomunikasi Elektronika Vol 14 No.1, Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe.
- [3] Safitri Nelly, Farhad Shahnia, Mohammad AS Masoum, 2016, “Coordination of single-phase rooftop PVs in unbalanced three-phase residential feeders for voltage profiles improvement”, Australian Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Taylor & Francis

- [4] Safitri Nelly, Rachmawati, Yassir, 2018, “Electrification, Decentralization and IT/OT Digitization of Grid-Connected Rooftop PVs in Residential Feeder”, GEASC (Global Engineering and Applied Science Conference) Fukuoka Japan.
- [5] Zamzami, Safitri, Nelly, Fauzi, 2018, “Non-uniform Rooftop PVs Distribution Effect to Improve Voltage Profile in Residential Feeder”, Jurnal Telkomnika, Vol. 16 Issue 4.
- [6] Yassir, 2019, “Optimization of Tilt Angle for Photovoltaic: Case Study Sabang-Indonesia”, IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, Volume 536, IOP Publishing.
- [7] Yassir, 2019, “Optimasi Sudut Penyimpangan Panel Surya Terhadap Garis Lintang dengan Metode Algoritma Genetika, Studi Kasus: Kampus Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe”, Proceeding Seminar Nasional Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe Vol.3 No.1 .
- [8] Naim Muhammad, 2017, “Rancangan Sistem Kelistrikan Plts Off Grid 1000 Watt Di Desa Mahalona Kecamatan Towuti”, Jurnal Ilmah Teknik Mesin Dinamika Volume 9 Nomor 1, ISBN : 2085-8817.
- [9] Naim Muhammad, 2017, “Rancangan Sistem Kelistrikan Plts On Grid 1500 Watt Dengan Back Up Battery Di Desa Timampu Kecamatan Towuti”, Jurnal Ilmah Teknik Mesin Dinamika Volume 8 Nomor 2, ISBN : 2085-8817.
- [10] Hasanuddin, 2019, “Perancangan Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Air Krueng Lhok Gob Kabupaten Pidie Jaya Sebagai Distributed Generation Pada Sistem Interkoneksi 150 Kv Aceh– Sumut”, Buku Laporan Penelitian, Politeknik Negeri Lhokseumawe.
- [11] Hasanuddin, 2016, “Optimasi Aliran Daya Sistem Kelistrikan Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam Berbasis Distributed Generation Dengan Menggunakan Metode Algoritma Genetik, Jurnal Energi” Elektrik Volume 5 Nomor 1, Universitas Malikussaleh Lhokseumawe.
- [12] Valerijs, “Stability of Power Systems with Large Amounts of Distributed Generation”, KTH Institution, Stockholm, Sweden, 2004